

K Means based Recommender System Model for Mobile Commerce using Cloud computing

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Abstract— Cloud computing is mainly used to make applications more scalable and maintainable as per user's demand. These features of this newly emerged modern technology of cloud can be used to make recommender systems more scalable and reliable. In this paper we present a Cloud based approach for designing a recommender system for Mobile users. In our approach we shall first divide our rating database in smaller parts based on commodities and then run recommendation algorithm by clustering users age and location, simultaneously on different cloud servers to get final result. Use of K means clustering to cluster user according to their interest is done.

Keywords— *Cloud Computing, K means clustering, Recommendation*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rise of Cloud computing as a new business computing model, the scale and depth of which a data can be mined and processed has increased immensely. Cloud computing is the practice of using a network of remote servers hosted on the Internet to store, manage, and process data, rather than a local server or a personal computer. We propose a model that can take advantage of this new technology to provide better and fast recommendations to user. A user "Z" will enter his Age and Location in system. Locations are arranged in ascending order of English speaking population. Using K means clustering we shall find proper cluster for this user "Z", opinion of majority people in the allotted cluster regarding commodity, will be counted and returned. We shall make use of different number of cloud Virtual Machines (VM) to host the review dataset related to a certain commodity. This way we can cluster users with same view together. Use of cloud paradigm will provide us more scalable, deep performance. In this paper we shall see our proposed system and results and analysis of system.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. Dataset Preparing:

For designing a dataset, we first take a book rating dataset in CSV format, which has ratings for about 3 books with their Title, ISBN, Year of Publication and Author. Our rating dataset consists of about 161238 users who have rated these three books on scale of 1 to 10. 1 means low and rating of 10 means high. We also have each users profile that consist of his age and location. Sample CSV format,

```
("User-ID";"ISBN";"Book-Rating")
("276725";"034545104X";"5")
```

B. Pre-processing of Dataset:

Our dataset is divided into different groups based on ratings related to a certain books. For Example Users rating "1" to Book "X" will be placed in Vector (X, 1), likewise users giving rating Book "X" as "2" will be places in Vector (X, 2), etc. For each book there will be 10 Vectors consisting UserID of User who gave it rating that may range from 1 to 10. All the matrices relating to a book are hosted on a separate cloud virtual machine. Sample Vector is shown below,

Evaluation (The Da Vinci Code, 8)
276725
276746
276751
276803
276828
276847

Table 1. Vector Showing UserID of users who have rated book "The Da Vinci Code" as 8 out of 10

Figure 1. Storage of rating vectors of each book on separate Virtual Machine.

C. Recommendation using K means:

After preparation of dataset, we use Microsoft Azure to create a cloud environment. Microsoft Azure provides basically three services, Compute, Storage, Fabric. As we are going to store our different datasets relating to a certain book on different cloud VMs, we are implementing in turn an IAAS (Infrastructure as a Service) model. Each books review set is given to a separate Virtual Machine, so when a new user enters his age and Location, it is simultaneous being compared with how the user having same Age and Location features, rated that book. We use azure concept of Worker Role and Web Role to implement a VM. Worker are VM without an IIS support, Webroles are VM with IIS support. We use both of them to implement our concept and they communicate with each other using Azure Queues.

K means is used to find proximity or relevance of user with other users based on his/her Age and Location. For location, they are arranged in ascending order of their English speaking population. Meaning a User of same age from USA will be more close to use of same age form Canada than that from Bangladesh, as USA and Canada have more English speaking population than Bangladesh. For a certain value of Age, Location we get nearest cluster of a User.

Figure 2. K-Means Clustering of Data on Cloud VM

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF SYSTEM

The system design as expected gave us flexibility to scale application. Also use of different VM to host rating dataset corresponding to certain commodity (book in this case) allowed us to use bigger review dataset for more precise and faster results. Parallel processing by different cloud virtual machines resulted in faster recommendations.

IV. CONCLUSION

This novel approach of dividing recommendation dataset across multiple cloud VMs not only gave us faster results but also widen the scope to process huge changing dataset of reviews. Use of such systems on e-commerce sites will largely benefit prospective buyers to buy most suited items based on recommendation from people of same age group, locality, culture and language.

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